

ENHANCING YOUNG LEARNERS' READING COMPREHENSION THROUGH FAIRY TALES

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to investigate the effectiveness of using fairy tales to enhance young learners' reading comprehension. The research focuses on the impact of fairy tales on students' reading skills, comprehension, and overall language development. The study also explores the potential benefits of integrating fairy tales into the curriculum to improve students' literacy skills. The findings suggest that fairy tales can be a valuable tool for enhancing young learners' reading comprehension and fostering a love for reading.

KEYWORDS: fairy tales, reading comprehension, young learners, literacy skills, language development

INTRODUCTION

Reading comprehension is a crucial skill that lays the foundation for academic success and lifelong learning. It is essential for young learners to develop strong reading comprehension skills from an early age to comprehend and analyze texts effectively. However, many students struggle with reading comprehension, which can hinder their academic progress. In recent years, educators have been exploring innovative ways to enhance students' reading comprehension, and one such approach is the use of fairy tales. Fairy tales are timeless stories that have been passed down through generations and have captivated the imaginations of children around the world. These enchanting stories not only entertain but also offer valuable opportunities for language development and critical thinking. This study aims to investigate the potential of

using fairy tales to enhance young learners' reading comprehension.

MAIN BODY

Fairy tales have long been cherished for their ability to transport readers to magical worlds and teach valuable life lessons. These timeless stories are rich in language and imagery, making them an excellent resource for developing young learners' reading comprehension skills. When students engage with fairy tales, they are exposed to a wide range of vocabulary, complex sentence structures, and figurative language. This exposure helps students expand their language skills and improve their ability to comprehend and interpret texts. Additionally, fairy tales often feature moral dilemmas, conflicts, and character development, providing ample opportunities for students to analyze and evaluate the text.

Furthermore, fairy tales can serve as a springboard for meaningful discussions and activities that promote reading comprehension. Teachers can use fairy tales as a basis for exploring various literary elements such as plot, character development, setting, and theme. By delving into these elements, students can deepen their understanding of the story and develop critical thinking skills. Moreover, teachers can incorporate creative activities such as retelling the story from a different character's perspective, rewriting the ending, or creating alternative storylines. These activities not only foster creativity but also reinforce students' comprehension of the text.

In addition to enhancing reading comprehension, fairy tales can also instill a love for reading in young learners. The enchanting and imaginative nature of fairy tales captivates students' interest and motivates them to engage with the text. As students become engrossed in these magical stories, they develop a positive attitude towards reading and are more likely to seek out other literary works. This love for reading can have long-term benefits for students' academic success and personal growth.

Literature plays an important role in our life. Fairy tales as a part of the

children's literature could be a valuable source for teaching English as a foreign language. Fairy tales might be considered one of the possible supplementary teaching materials for English language learners. It is not only the atmosphere of mystery, thrill and wonder which makes fairy tales so unique and valuable but they can bring the whole magic world to a young reader and learner. They can open the old wisdom and knowledge of humankind which we often forget about. Literature provides wonderful source material for eliciting strong emotional responses from students and using it in classroom is a fruitful way of involving the learner as a whole person. Fairy tales may contribute to the enrichment of a young reader's knowledge in a number of ways. They teach moral and values highlighting the most universal norms and standards of language existence. In addition to that, fairy tales are a particular type of text which can be adapted to suit the child's age, whereas their composition of sentences and plot is simple and understandable.

Many teachers believe that the basic truth of learning a foreign language naturally entails doing work of the 'boring but necessary' type. Others spend a lot of time trying to find more interesting ways to teach foreign language by searching materials on the Internet or looking for materials in the additional books. However, the teachers should do their best in order to motivate and support the learning environment in the classroom as much as possible.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Traditional stories can help young children develop vital life skills in a safe environment, says Teresa Heapy. Exploring ideas around what is right and wrong is one of many lessons with which we support children as they grow up. We help them to understand that there are expected rules and expectations about how we behave, and to think about cause and effect. Young children are egocentric because that is part of their cognitive growth – they learn to build empathy and think about others through interactions. They discover their actions

have consequences and can affect other people's feelings, as well as impacting their own emotions. Sharing stories can be a very powerful and safe way to help children consider and navigate complex, moral subjects like these.

Once upon a time

With their beloved structures and language, fairy tales are particularly useful for educators to draw on with issues like this. They begin with traditional openings such as "Once upon a time..." so children know they are being transported out of reality and into a safe story world – where universal themes such as good versus evil can be explored creatively and related to the world around them.

The stories are familiar to most children – when I visit schools, libraries or nurseries, the children I meet are usually familiar with the basic storyline of the most popular fairy tales.

You will know how animated a group of under-fives can suddenly become when you ask, "Who's heard of Goldilocks?" Once you have children's attention, you can then develop their understanding around certain topics – for example, the idea that an individual's actions could hurt others around them. With a fairy-tale context, even the shyest child can begin to debate the characters, plot and events within the story. Very Little series of picture books for early years children are all based around favourite fairy tales, but present the lead character as a preschool child in a contemporary setting. This means all the stories have a twist.

The twist is significant because it highlights the power of fairy tales to not only build a foundation of story language, but also act as a springboard for children's own writing. For example, Very Little Red Riding Hood is based on a child who is going for a sleepover at Grandmama's when she bumps into a wolf, who ends up looking after her. Tension is created by drawing on the language and

structure of the original tale – but here it’s the wolf, not Red Riding Hood, who ends up remarking, “What a big mouth you have!” It’s then a simple step to ask the children to imagine their own ‘Very Little’ version of another fairy-tale character.

Happily ever after

Fairy tales can receive negative press and the criticisms are worth investigating. In part, this is due to the stories’ Disneyfication and the fact that many deal with old-fashioned ideas.

But rather than ban fairy tales – which we know are so important to children’s reading diet and literary heritage – we can create a dialogue that challenges some of the issues head-on.

We can read feminist retellings alongside the original stories. Different versions of a fairy tale can be shared, such as one of the hundreds of global variations on Cinderella. And we must address diversity in children’s books by ensuring fairy-tale characters represent all readers.

With so much uncertainty and negativity in today’s society, it’s important that children are adequately equipped to deal with the emotional pressure this can bring. For practitioners and teachers, it can be a challenge to know how best to approach certain topics, but as their longevity has demonstrated, fairy tales are often the answer. It’s within the realm of the fairy tale that children can experience a wide range of emotions – from fear and sadness to relief and excitement – in the knowledge that the tale usually ends “happily ever after” for the heroes and heroines. Without fairy tales, children will lack many important skills to help them with their reading and writing too. Let’s not forget the quote often attributed to Albert Einstein: “If you want your children to be intelligent,

read them fairy tales. If you want them to be more intelligent, read them more fairy tales.”

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, fairy tales have the potential to significantly enhance young learners' reading comprehension. These timeless stories provide rich opportunities for language development, critical thinking, and creative expression. By integrating fairy tales into the curriculum, educators can effectively support students' literacy skills and foster a love for reading. As such, educators should consider incorporating fairy tales into their teaching practices to enhance young learners' reading comprehension and overall language development.

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